

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF APHORISMS IN ENGLISH AND
UZBEK

Salayeva Gulrano Zaribbay qizi

Master's degree student of english
linguistics department
Urgench state university
solayevagulrano@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The aim of the article is to compare analysis of aphorisms about education in English and Uzbek. Furthermore, the purpose of the article is to highlight the grammatical and semantic differences between English and Uzbek aphorisms. Types and their meanings are analysed carefully and given examples which shows specific features of aphorisms in two the contacting languages.

Key words: aphorism, literal translation , proverbs, equivalence

Аннотация

Цель статьи – сравнительный анализ афоризмов об образовании на английском и узбекском языках. Цель статьи - выделить грамматические и семантические различия между английскими и узбекскими афоризмами. Тщательно проанализированы типы и их значения и приведены примеры, показывающие специфические особенности афоризмов в двух контактирующих языках.

Ключевые слова: афоризмы, дословный перевод, пословица, эквивалентность.

Annotatsiya

Maqolaning maqsadi ingliz va o'zbek tillarida ta'lim haqidagi aforizmlarning tahlilini solishtirishdir, va bundan tashqari, ingliz va o'zbek aforizmlari o'rtasidagi grammatik va semantik farqlarni yoritib berishdir. Turlari va ularning ma'nolari

sinchiklab tahlil qilinadi,, aforizmlarning o‘ziga xos xususiyatlarini ko‘rsatuvchi misollar keltirilib, ularda aforizmlarning ikki tilda aloqasini kursatib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: aforizmlar, so'zma-so'z tarjima, maqollar, ekvivalentlik

INTRODUCTION

As we know, it is also important to describe and classify aphorisms in English and Uzbek. An aphorism (from Greek ἀφορισμός: aphorismos, denoting 'delimitation', 'distinction', and 'definition') is a concise, terse, laconic, or memorable expression of a general truth or principle.[1] Aphorisms are often handed down by tradition from generation to generation. The concept is generally distinct from those of an adage, brocard, chiasmus, epigram, maxim (legal or philosophical), principle, proverb, and saying; although some of these concepts may be construed as types of aphorism. Often, aphorisms are distinguished from other short sayings by the need for interpretation to make sense of them. The concept of "aphorism" was introduced by Hippocrates. So he called in the IV century BC. e. his treatise on diseases and the art of their cure, and wrote in the preface: "Life is short, art is long-lived." For a long time, the term "aphorism" was associated precisely with medicine, and it acquired the meaning of a moralizing saying only in the 16th century. Aphoristic statements are quoted in writings as well as in our daily speech. The fact that they contain a truth gives them a universal acceptance. On the contrary to proverbs the origin of wise words belong to an exact person (writer, poet, publicist, philosopher, scientist, statesman and etc) and retain its individuality.

Analysis and results.

The purpose of an aphorism is to convey a message to people that is generally regarded as a universal moral or truth. Therefore, when creating an aphorism, it is important to identify your audience and the purpose of your writing in order to convey an appropriate message. Writers often create general statements in their texts in order to convey a moral or philosophical idea they hold to be universally true. Furthermore, Aphorisms are often used to teach a lesson while speaking in plain terms. For example, "A bad penny always turns up" is an aphorism for the fact that bad people or things are

bound to turn up in life. We just have to deal with them when they do. This aphorism is motivation. These types of aphorisms lead people to success. And in a word, aphorisms teach us to look at life with confidence. "When cats away the mice will play", we can see from this, the words, "mice" and "cats" refer to people and there is equivalence for it in Uzbek: "*Sulaymon o`ldi devlar qutuldi*". Besides, we can see another examples: "Time and tide wait for no man" - *Vaqt - g`animat, o`tsa nadomat*. "The least foolish is wise" - *Ahmoqlarga bosh bo`lguncha donolarga yosh bo`l*. These words of wisdom are mainly semantically translated into Uzbek and also the Uzbek equivalents are determined for them. Sometimes, we can come across the aphorisms that are translated literally. Literal translation is a translation of a text done by translating each word separately, without looking at how the words are used together in a phrase or sentence. For instance, "All is one, one is all" – "Hamma bir kishi uchun, bir kishi hamma uchun" Here, "All and One" is generalised, they refer to people. In this table, you can see additional aphorisms which are given with Uzbek equivalents:

ENGLISH	UZBEK
Early bird gets the worm	Erta turganga Xudo beradi
It is never too late to learn	O`rganishning erta-kechi bo`lmaydi
Action speak louder than words	Harakatda barakat
Jack of all trades and master of none	Yuz hunarni chala bilgandan, bir hunarning ustasi bo`lgan yaxshi
Go farther and fare worse	Boriga rozi bo`lib, yo`g`iga sabr qilib yashash kerak

Here are some additional examples of aphorisms with explanations regarding their messages:

" 'Tis better to have loved and lost/ than never to have loved at all." – Alfred, Lord Tennyson

All work and no play makes Jack a dull boy.

This statement is used to emphasize the necessary balance between work and leisure. If all we do is work, it's more difficult to maintain an interesting personality.

Discussion

Aphorisms are widely found in literature. In fact, many aphorisms used in literature break through their literary use and become relevant in their own sense, apart from the original work in which they appeared. Aphorisms often use metaphors, creative imagery, or other literary terms to express ideas.

And since they're universal truths about life, they help persuade your reader to accept your message. We see this in literature all the time. Many are used in everyday conversation due to their catchy and witty word choice. In Harper Lee's *To Kill a Mockingbird*, she expresses her message regarding ignorance through this commonly quoted line:

▪ You never really understand a person until you consider things from his point of view...until you climb into his skin and walk around in it.

In William Shakespeare's *Romeo and Juliet*, he expresses that names are meaningless and do not predetermine a person or thing's traits through Juliet's line:

▪ What's in a name? That which we call a rose/ By any other word would smell as sweet.

Aphorisms are so common that we hardly think twice about them.

But not today. Today, I'll define aphorism and show you how these handy little sayings make your writing more memorable.

Research Methodology

How does an aphorism differ from adage or proverb? Truthfully, there aren't huge differences between the three. That's why aphorisms, adages, and proverbs are synonyms for each other. But one key difference is that for a phrase to be truly aphoristic, it needs to be a short Proverbs, on the other hand, can be much longer than aphorisms and adages.

Take this proverb, for example:

▪ "Early to bed a7nd early to rise makes a man healthy, wealthy, and wise." It's a great saying, but it's not something you'd necessarily repeat over the dinner table.

Now compare that proverb to this famous aphorism:

▪ "The early bird gets the worm."

Both sayings highlight the benefits of waking up early. But, the aphorism is a sweet, short phrase Now that we've covered the aphorism definition, are you ready for more examples? Do you believe that a penny saved is a penny earned? If you do, you agree with George Herbert's famous aphorism from his book, *Outlandish Proverbs*.

The original dictum said, "A penny spar'd is twice got," but it's adapted over the years for modern English.

Another aphorism that's adapted is, "Don't count your chickens before they hatch." This quote originated from Thomas Howell in *New Sonnets and Pretty Pamphlets*. It originally read, "Count not they chickens that unhatched be..." The meaning? Don't count on things that haven't happened yet because something unexpected could occur.

▪It's better safe than sorry, right?

Speaking of being safe, that's another aphorism example that you've probably heard before.

▪"Better safe than sorry" is a piece of wisdom from Samuel Lover's book, *Rory O'More*.

Conclusion

In the process of analysis it can be concluded that English aphorisms are translated from a semantic point of view. Through the analysis of aphorisms in English and Uzbek, the Uzbek language can develop linguistic culture. Many aphorisms were created in ancient times and still with the people who are their creators. Aphorisms are popular, passed down from generation to generation and live for centuries

References

1. https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Aphorism#cite_ref-1
2. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/comparative-linguistic-analysis-of-uzbek-and-englishaphorisms>
3. <https://kpi.ua/en/aphorism-education%20>
4. <https://www.uwed.uz/uz/news/fulltext/1616>
5. Cambridge advanced learner`s dictionary 4th edition

6. Kimsanova G. “ Comparative analysis of English proverbs and sayings expressing senility and youth” .
7. <https://maqollar.uz/page/12>
8. Radin. P “A study in American English Mythology” New York 1992.
9. J. Raymond. 1956. Tensions in Proverbs: More Light on International Understanding.